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ABSTRACT

In medical images noise and artifacts are presented due to the measurement techniques and instrumentation. Because of the noise present in the medical images, physicians are unable to obtain required information from the images. The paper proposes a noise reduction method for both computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) which fuses the Curvelet transform based method. The performance is analysed by computing Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR). The results show the proposed method can obtain enhanced visual and de-noise effect.

KEYWORDS: Curvelet Transform, Medical Image de-noise, PSNR.

INTRODUCTION

Medical images are often exposed to various noise interferences in the process of generation, transmission and recording. Image denoising by an appropriate method is very important before the high-level process of edge detection, image segmentation, feature extraction, pattern recognition and on. The image denoising method can be divided into two categories: one is the spatial domain methods, in which image smoothed by convolution of smoothing template and, in order to suppress or eliminating noise. The other is frequency domain methods, in which the image is filtered by a suitable frequency band-pass filter after transformation of the image, and then gets the denoised image by the inverse transform. Spatial domain methods includes mean filtering, median filtering, adaptive noise filtering and morphological filtering, frequency filter includes Fourier transform and image de-noising using wavelet and ultra-wavelet.

In recent years, wavelet theory has developed rapidly, and because of its capability of good time-frequency localization and multi-resolution analysis, it has a very wide range of applications in various fields of image processing. In the field de-noising, wavelet theory is attached an importance by many scholars, who denoised signals using wavelet transform, and obtained very good results [1] [2]. Because of advantages and potential in denoising, wavelet analysis has been a research focus, and get some achievements. At present, the wavelet denoising method can be broadly classified into three categories. The first method proposed by Mallat is wavelet transform modulus maxima denoising. The second category is correlation denoising method based on wavelet transform and the third method is threshold method proposed by Donoho [3] [4] [5] [6]. Reconstruction filter of modulus maximum is to reconstruct the signal by using the modulus maxima of wavelet coefficients at all scales of the signal. The modulus maximum of wavelet coefficients of signal contains the peak variability and singularity. If these signals can be reconstructed from the maximum value, and the singularity of signal can be changed by dealing with the modulus maxima of wavelet coefficients, so the corresponding singularity can be removed by inhabiting the certain maxima of coefficients, above is the basic idea of modulus maximum reconstruction filter. Modulus maximum reconstruction filter is based on signal and noise presented various properties in wavelet transform with the different scale, it has a good theoretical basis and more stable filtering performance, it is less depend on noise and do not need to know the noise variance, so it has superiority especially for low SNR when the signal filtering. However, it has a fundamental drawback, that is, there is a problem comes from the reconstruction of wavelet coefficients by modulus maxima in filtering process, which makes the calculation of this method is greatly increased, while the actual filtering effect is not very satisfactory.

Wavelet denoising based on signal correlation and noise is constructing the corresponding rules on different expression of wavelet transform at different scales, then the wavelet coefficients of signal and noise are processed, as well as the substance is completely removed the reduced coefficient of the noise, maximize the effective signal to retain the wavelet coefficients at the same time. After the wavelet transform of the signal, the wavelet coefficients of signal at each scale have obvious correlation, particularly near the edge of the signal, the relevance is more obvious, but the wavelet coefficients corresponding to scale of noise is no such obvious correlation. Wavelet threshold denoising method is able to concentrate signal energy to a small number of wavelet coefficients, while the transformations of white noise in any orthogonal basis is still the white noise, and have the same magnitude. In contrast, the wavelet coefficients magnitude of signal are inevitable larger than those of noise whose energy scattered and smaller. To select an appropriate threshold and remove the wavelet coefficients of the noise by thresholding can achieved the purpose of retaining useful signals. For the defects of Wavelet transform, Candes and Donoho proposed Curvelet that more suitable for analysing signals in the high singularity.

Curvelet transform has a good selection and identification of the direction to effectively approximate the image details of the edge of and texture, Curvelet transform in the field of image fusion can better describe the characteristics of the original image, thereby improving the quality of fusion, now the second generation of Curvelet transform is mainly used for image processing [10] [11].

CURVELET TRANSFORM

Continuous Curvelet Transform

Continuous Curvelet transform signal represent as inner product of basis functions and signal function (or function) to denote the sparse representation [7] [8] [9], expressed as:

$$C(j, l, k) = \langle f, \varphi_{j,l,k} \rangle \quad (1)$$

where $\varphi_{j,l,k}$ is Curvelet function, j, l, k , respectively, is scale, orientation, location parameters. Curvelet transform implements in the frequency domain. To define a window function $W(r)$, $r \in (1/2, 2)$; and a angle function $V(t)$, $t \in [1, 1]$.

$$\sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} W^2(2^j r) = 1, r \in (3/4, 3/2) \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} V^2(t-1) = 1, t \in (-1/2, 1/2) \quad (3)$$

$$U_j(r, \theta) = 2^{-3j/4} W(2^{-j} r) V\left(\frac{2^{(j/2)} \theta}{2\pi}\right) \quad (4)$$

where $[j/2]$ is an integer part of $j/2$. The support area U_j is a wedge shaped area come from support area W and V .

To define the curvelet at scale 2^j the direction θ , translation parameter (k_1, k_2) is

$$\varphi_{j,l,k}(x) = \varphi_j(R_{\theta}(x - x_k^{(j,k)})) \quad (5)$$

$$x_k(j, l) = R_{\theta}^{-1}(k_1 \cdot 2^{-j}, k_2 \cdot 2^{-j/2}) \quad (6)$$

Curvelet transform can be expressed as:

$$c(j, l, k) = \langle f, \varphi_{j,l,k} \rangle = \int R^{2f(x)} \bar{\varphi}_{j,l,k}(x) dx \quad (7)$$

Discrete Curvelet Transform

The input is $f[t_1, t_2]$ ($0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq n$) in the Cartesian coordinates corresponding to the local window, the discrete form of Curvelet transform is

$$c^D(j, l, k) = \sum_{0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq n} f[t_1, t_2] \bar{\varphi}_{j,l,k}^D[t_1, t_2] \quad (8)$$

Aided by a band pass function

$$\psi(\omega_1) = \sqrt{(\omega_1 / 2)^2 - (\omega_1)^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{to define } \psi_j(\omega_1) = \psi(2^{-j} \omega_1) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } s_{\theta_1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -\tan \theta_1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

It is not equally spaced, but the slope is equal intervals. Define

$$\tilde{U}_j(\omega) = \psi_j(\omega_1) V_j(\omega) \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{U}_j(\omega) = \psi_j(\omega_1) V_j(s_{\theta_1} \omega) = \tilde{U}_j(s_{\theta_1} \omega) \quad (13)$$

PROPOSED METHOD

The following are steps of image denoise using Curvelet generally:

- Step 1: preprocessing the image.
- Step 2: Curvelet transform the image.
- Step 3: calculate the threshold of transform coefficients for each offspring, deal with coefficient.
- Step 4: To do Curvelet inverse transform to obtain denoised image.

The following are steps of CT image and MRI denoise using Curvelet:

- Step 1: CT and MRI images with noise decomposed into low frequency coefficients and high frequency coefficients at each scale by Curvelet transform.
- Step 2: To estimate the noise variance using Monte-Carlo method with the scale of sub-band , and then process high-frequency coefficients at all scales , the hard threshold function is defined as

$$T(x) = \begin{cases} x, & |x| > \lambda \\ 0, & |x| \leq \lambda \end{cases}$$

where $\lambda = 3\sigma$

- Step 3: Apply IFFT to high-frequency coefficients and low-frequency coefficients, get the thedenoised image.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 (a) Noisy CT brain image with PSNR = 20.3dB (b) Wavelet de-noising with PSNR= 42.5 and (c) Curvelet de-noising with PSNR = 46.3 dB.

Fig.2 (a) Noisy MRI brain image with PSNR = 23.22dB (b) Wavelet de-noising with PSNR= 46.7dB and (c) Curvelet de-noising with PSNR = 49.5 dB.

According to the above results, curvelet de-noising promises better visual effect than wavelet de-noising method.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the proposed method of image denoising with Curvelet transform brought better denoising effect and visual effects than that of method using Wavelet. Curvelet transform can accurately express very little edge using very less non-zero coefficient to guarantee the better ability of image representation than wavelet does on lower mean square error in the noisy environment.

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